

JOB DEMAND AS A PREDICTOR OF TEACHERS' PRODUCTIVITY IN SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN NORTH-EAST, NIGERIA

Ezugu Appollonia Nneka¹ & A. U. Okoronka²

¹University Secondary School, Modibbo Adama University, Yola

²Physical Sciences Education Department, Modibbo Adama University, Yola

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10032307>

Abstract

The study investigated the level to which teachers' job demands could predict teachers' job productivity in Senior Secondary Schools in North-East, Nigeria. One research question was answered and one hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study adopted a correlational survey research design. The population for the study was 22,733 subjects which comprised of 965 principals and 21,768 teachers from Senior Secondary Schools in six states (Adamawa, Bauchi, Borno, Gombe, Taraba and Yobe) drawn from North-East, Nigeria. Multistage sampling technique was used in selecting the sample for the study. Four states were purposively drawn for the study because of insurgency. These are Adamawa, Bauchi, Gombe and Yobe. 50% of educational zones from each of the selected states for the study was applied. Random sampling technique was used in selecting the educational zones from the states selected for the study. The sample size for the study was 1,221 subjects which comprised 225 principals and 996 teachers. Teachers' Job demand Questionnaire was developed by the researcher from the review of literature and a 12-item Structured Questionnaire titled "Teachers' Productivity Questionnaire" was adopted from Ayeni (2020). The instruments were face-validated by 8 experts in school of education. In order to determine the reliability of the instruments, the test-retest method was used to collect data from respondents in the South east, Nigeria and data collected were analysed using the Cronbach Alpha Method. The results of the test yielded reliability indices of 0.892 and 0.811 for the Teachers Job demands Questionnaire and Teachers' Productivity Questionnaire respectively. The data relating to research question were analysed using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation while linear regression was used in analysing data relating to hypothesis, which was tested at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study showed, among others, that the level of teachers' job demands is high and that teachers job demands is a significant predictor of teachers' productivity in Senior Secondary Schools in North East, Nigeria. It was recommended that even though teachers' job demand is high, the job demand items such as workload should be moderated, solution to interpersonal conflicts among teachers and principals be sorted and improvisation of instructional materials be made available to help teachers cope well with work for higher productivity.

Keywords: Job Demand, Predictor, Teachers' Productivity

Introduction

Job demand is the ability to cope with workload, ability to be punctual to school, difficulty in covering the syllabi or work before examination, ability to improvise instructional materials for lessons and the extent of work conflict. Job demands can also be described as the level of interpersonal conflicts among teachers and principals, extent of time pressure and complexities of tasks (managing resources to cope with work and health).

Bakker and Demerouti (2018) stated that job demands are the aspects of work that cost energy, like workload, complex tasks and conflicts. Job demand may initiate a health impairment process due to exposure to daily workload which could transform into chronic overload over a long period. In this case, job demand leads to chronic exhaustion and may eventually result in physical health problems (including cardiovascular diseases). Kabir (2019) opined that generally, studies show that teaching is characterized by high level occupational demand and work pressure. Furthermore, that research work conducted in United States of America by Kosgel, Mise, Odera and Ayugi (in Kabir 2019) revealed that there is a high level of job demand in teaching profession. Also, the teachers and operational staff at school confirmed that they felt job stress due to the unpredictable job demand of the school.

Uoro (2018) carried out a study on occupational stress and its effect on the job effectiveness of lecturers in Federal Universities in Cross-River and Akwa Ibom states of Nigeria. The results indicated that stress from job factors such as workload, facilities, career development requirements and organizational climate significantly and jointly predicted job effectiveness of lecturers while interpersonal relationships and funding were not significant predictors. Vissy and Arum (2018) expressed that job demand causes stress and must be addressed immediately because it is detrimental to teachers and staff and will ultimately harm the organization.

Elujekwute, Nyitar and Elujekwute (2021) observed that the negative effects of teachers' stress include reduction in work performance and output, inability to manage time or delegate duties, feelings of alienation and inadequacy, loss of confidence and motivation, increasing introversion, irritability with colleagues, unwillingness to cooperate, frequent irritational conflict at work, withdrawal of supportive relationships, loss of appetite for the job and accident proneness. Prominent among these factors are working conditions, delay in promotion, lack of resources for teaching, workload with nonteaching duties, lack of in-service training, and pupils' poor attitude to work. These factors affect their level of job performance and since teachers are the custodians of skills and knowledge that groom the children into the expectation of curriculum designers, the occupational stress and working environment of teachers during the process of discharging their duties or expected tasks becomes things of great concern for educational managers and heads of various institutions, particularly secondary schools.

Kanja, Wang'eri and Mwangi (2022) carried out a study on teachers' workload stress as a correlate of job satisfaction in international secondary schools in Nairobi city, Kenya. The study investigated relationship between teachers' workload stress and job satisfaction. The findings indicated that teachers who were categorized as having high level of workload stress had the lowest score of job satisfaction. The results further indicated that teachers' workload stress had a significant negative relationship with job satisfaction score. It was recommended that school managers ought to look into approaches that could reduce teachers' workload stress and improve their job satisfaction.

Ndambo, Maithya and Mwaura (2021) carried out a study on the effect of teaching workload on teachers' performance in public secondary schools in Kitui county. The study established there is statistically significant relationship between teaching workload and teachers' performance $P\text{-value} = 0.001 < 0.05$ level of significance. The study concluded that teachers felt they had a high teaching workload hence lacking ample time for lesson preparation and this made them feel they had prepared their students for assessment. The study recommended the need for school principals to balance the teachers' workload for them to become productive by getting enough time for lessons preparation.

Yusuf, Olufunke and Valentine (2015) carried out a study on causes and impact of stress on teachers' productivity as expressed by primary school teachers in Osun state, Nigeria. The result revealed that majority of primary school teachers

were stressed on the job and this had negative impact on their productivity. The study also revealed that lack of job satisfaction and inadequate school facilities were major causes of stress among primary school teachers. Actually, stress on the job brings about employee's exhaustion and burnout and results to low productivity.

Uwannah, Eteete and Mark (2019) stated that productivity has been defused as effort made towards achieving organization effectiveness with the least available resources; it is the ratio of output produced by an organization to the resources used in the process. Tijani and Abdullahi (2021) expressed that teachers' productivity can be measured using the following variables: marking of students' notebooks, students counselling, students' academic performance, involvement in extracurricular activities, adequate coverage of syllabus, use of instructional aids, allowing questions from students and communicating in understandable language.

Chen, Li, Xia and He (2017) opined that job demands have been identified as one of the most common sources of work-related stress and further stated that as job demands increase, workers physiological and psychological resources are increasingly drained. This will cause negative work outcomes if enough requisite resources of individuals are not available. Job demands could affect teachers by draining their resources and tasking them psychologically and physiologically. With these, one can say that job demands constitute a problem in every organization, especially in the education sector (teaching in particular).

It is observed that job demands drain employee's resources and make it difficult for them to cope with their job and could affect their productivity. The problem of the study is that the extent to which teachers job demand affect teachers in carrying out their primary assignment is not known. This prompted the need to investigate or carry out research to determine the level at which job demand predicts teachers' productivity.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to investigate the level to which teachers' job demand could predict their productivity in senior secondary schools in North-East, Nigeria.

Research Question

What is the level of teachers' job demand in senior secondary schools in North-East, Nigeria?

Hypothesis

Teachers' job demand does not significantly predict their productivity in senior secondary schools in North-East, Nigeria.

Methodology

Research Design

Correlational survey research design was adopted for this study. Correlational survey research design is suitable for this study because in this study, data on independent variable (Job demand) and dependent variable (teachers' productivity) were collected and correlated. The extent to which independent variable predicted the dependent variable were determined.

Area of Study

The study was conducted in North-East, Nigeria (Adamawa, Bauchi, Borno, Gombe, Taraba and Yobe)

Population for the Study

The population for the study is a total of 22,733 subjects which comprised of 965 principals and 21, 768 teachers in senior secondary schools in North-East, Nigeria i.e. Adamawa, Bauchi, Borno, Gombe, Taraba and Yobe States respectively. The distribution of principals and teachers in senior secondary schools in various states and number of educational zones are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Population Distribution

States	Educational Zones	Principals	Teachers
Adamawa	5	274	5,731
Bauchi	3	214	4,941
Borno	4	32	2,078
Gombe	3	111	2,460
Taraba	10	285	3,393
Yobe	3	49	3,165
Total	28	965	21,768

Sources: post primary schools management Board Yola, Adamawa State, Ministry of Education, Bauchi State, ministry of Education Gombe, Gombe State, Ministry of Education Jalingo, Taraba State, Ministry of Education Maiduguri, Borno State and Ministry of Education Damaturu, yobe State.

Sample and Sampling Techniques

The researcher used four out of the six states in North-East, Nigeria selected through purposive sampling due to insurgency. The states are Adamawa, Bauchi, Gombe and Taraba. Multistage sampling technique was used in selecting the sample for the study (principals and teachers) from the educational zones in the four states and the researcher selected 50% of education zones in each of the states as follows: Adamawa-3, Bauchi-2, Gombe-2 and Taraba-5. Simple random sampling technique was used in selecting the education zones from the selected states. Nwanna (2005) parameter was applied in selecting the sample size for the study. According to Nwanna (Ibid), if the population of the study is a few hundreds, 40% or more sample size will do; if many hundreds, 20% will do; if a few hundreds, 10% sample size will do, and if several thousands, 5% or less will do. To select the sample size of principals, 20% was applied and the following were obtained; 40% of 156=62 for Adamawa, 40% of 16=64 for Bauchi, 40% of 71=28 for Gombe and 40% of 177=71 for Taraba, making a total of 225 principals. In selecting the sample size for teachers, 10% was used with the exception of Bauchi state which 5% was applied because the number is more and is several thousands. For Adamawa state, 10% of 3,701 is 370, for Bauchi state, 5% of 4,025 is 201, for Gombe state, 10% of 1,805, is 181, for Taraba state, 10% 2,439 is 244. This gave a total of 996. Therefore, the sample size for the study is 1221 subjects: 225 for principals and 996 for teachers.

Instruments for Data Collection

The instruments that were used for data collection in this study were: a 10-item structured questionnaire for teachers titled ‘Job Demand Questionnaire’ and a 12- item questionnaire for principals titled “Teachers Productivity Questionnaire”. The job demand questionnaire was constructed by the researcher after a thorough review of literature and Teachers’ productivity questionnaire was adopted from Ayeni (2020). The items on both instruments were placed on 5-point rating scale. Respondents were required to tick the options which best describes their opinions as follows;

Very High Level (VHL) 5 points

High Level (HL) 4 points

Moderate Level (ML) 3 points

Low Level (LL) 2 points

Very Low Level (VLL) 1 point

Validation of the Instruments

Eight experts from the faculty of Education, Modibbo Adamawa University (MAU), Yola, face-validated the instruments. Four of the experts were from Physical Sciences Education Department, one from Technology Education Department, and three from Life and Environmental Science Education Department. They were given the title of the study, the research questions and the hypotheses and then requested to appraise the content, language, relevance, and adequacy of the instrument to collect data for the purpose of this study. All the suggestions and recommendations from the validations were carefully considered and used in the draft of the final instrument.

Reliability of the Instruments

In order to determine reliability of the instruments, 120 copies of the instruments were administered to principals and teachers in twelve secondary schools in South East, Nigeria using test - retest method. Ninety-six copies of the Job Demand questionnaire were administered to the teachers at two-week intervals while 24 copies of the teachers’ productivity questionnaire were administered to the 12 principals at two-week intervals. To determine the internal consistency of the instrument, the responses of the respondent were subjected to reliability analysis using Cronbach Alpha method. Reliability coefficients of the two instruments were 0.892 for the job demand questionnaire and 0.811 for the teachers’ productivity questionnaire. Based on these reliability coefficients it was concluded that both instruments have high internal consistency.

Method of Data Analysis

The data collected for this study were analysed using the statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) Version 23. The data on the research question was analysed with the descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation. The real limits of numbers of the responses categories of the five-point rating scale were used to determine the decision point for the means that was used for the research questions.

Response category	Point	Lower Limit	Upper Limit
Very High Level	5	4.5	5.00
High Level	4	3.5	4.49
Moderate Level	3	2.5	3.39
Low Level	2	1.5	2.49
Very Low Level	1	0.5	1.49

In this study, the grand mean score was used to determine the levels of factors in independent variable and dependent variable based on true limits of numbers. Linear regression statistic was used in analysing the data relating to hypothesis that was tested at 0.05 level of significance. It was used because the researcher wanted to predict the dependent variables based on the value of the independent variable. In order to take decision on the hypothesis, if the computed *p* value is less than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected, which implies that job demand factor

contributed significantly in predicting teacher’s productivity. On the other hand, if the computed *p*-value was greater than 0.05 level of significance, the hypothesis will be upheld.

Results

The result of the data analysis for the study are presented in line with the research question and hypothesis as follows:

Research Question 1: What is the level of teachers’ Job demand in senior secondary schools?

In order to answer this research question, the data relating to it were collected and analyzed using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation and the results are presented in table 2

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Responses on the level of Teacher’s Job Demand

S/N	Items	Mean	S.D	Remark
1	Ability to cope with work load	3.98	.960	High Level
2	Ability to be punctual at school	3.91	.926	High Level
3	Ability to cover scheme of work before examination	3.82	1.001	High Level
4	Ability to catch with meetings and deadlines	3.77	.943	High Level
5	Ability to improvise instructional materials	3.66	1.013	High Level
6	Ability to cope with work conflict	3.72	.935	High Level
7	Ability to cope with interpersonal conflicts among teachers and principals	3.77	.937	High Level
8	Ability to cope with work	3.84	.937	High Level
9	Extent of time pressure	3.75	.911	High Level
10	Managing resources to cope with work	3.70	1.007	High Level
Grand Mean		3.79		High Level

N=958(Total Number of respondents)

Table 2 shows the mean and standard deviation of the respondents on level of teacher’s job demand. The mean of the 10 items on job demand ranges from 3.66 for “Ability to improvise instructional materials” to 3.98 for “Ability to cope with your work load”. The variability of the responses ranges from 0.911 for “extent of time pressure” to 1.013 for “Ability to improvise instructional materials”. The table also shows the grand mean of the items to be 3.79. Based on the above results, both the grand mean and the mean of the individual items are high. Therefore, the level of teacher’s job demands is high in senior secondary schools in North-East, Nigeria.

Hypothesis Testing

The hypothesis was analysed using linear regression at 0.05 level of significance.

H₀₁: Teachers’ job demand does not significantly predict their productivity in senior secondary schools in North-East Nigeria.

Table 3a: ANOVA Summary Regression Table of Prediction of Teachers’ Job Demand and Teachers’ Productivity in Senior Secondary Schools in North-East, Nigeria

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Squares	F	Sig
1. Regression	9.764	1	9.764		.000b
Residual	48.621	198	.246	39.69	
TOTAL	58.386	199			

a. Dependent variable: Level of teacher’s productivity

b. Predictors: (constant) Job Demands.

Results of the of the analysis in table 2a shows summary of ANOVA used to test whether teacher’s job demand is a significant predictor of teacher’s productivity in senior secondary schools in North-East, Nigeria. The results revealed that teachers’ job demands are significant predictors of teacher’s productivity in North-East, Nigeria as *p*-values 0.000 is less than 0.05 significant level and the null hypothesis is rejected.

Table 3b: Model Summary of Prediction Between Teacher’s Job Demand and Teacher’s productivity

MODEL R	R SQUARE	ADJUSTED R SQUARE	Std .Error of the estimate.
1	.409a	.167	.49554

a) Predictors: (constant), job Demands

The results in table 2b shows a model summary which shows how the independent variable explains the variance in the dependent variable. The results show that the teacher’s job demand explained 16.3%of the variance in Teacher’s productivity in senior secondary schools. Teacher’s job demand and teacher’s productivity in senior secondary schools were found to have moderate positive relationship which is indicated by R-value of 0.409. Teacher’s job demand does not significantly predict their productivity in senior secondary schools in North-East, Nigeria.

Table 3c: Regression Coefficients of Prediction Between Teacher’s Job Demand and Teacher’s Productivity

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients B	Standardized Coefficients Std. Error Beta	T	Sig	
1.(constant)	2.257	.228	9.883	.000	
Job Demand	.374	.059	.409	6.306	.000

Dependent Variable: teachers’ productivity.

The results in table 2c, indicates the Beta coefficient of the regression analysis of teacher’s job demand and teachers’ productivity. The result shows a beta coefficient of 0.409, *t*=6.306, *p*=0.000, <0.05. This indicates that teacher’s job demand significantly predicted teacher’s productivity.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study on teacher’s job demand as a predictor of teacher’s productivity revealed that teacher’s job demand significantly predicted teacher’s productivity. The finding is in line with the finding of Uoro (2018) and that of Ndambo, Maithya, Mwaura (2021). The finding of this study disagreed with of Kanja, Wangaeri and Mwangi (2022) which indicated that teachers’ who were categorized as having high level of workload stress had the lowest score of job satisfaction. The result further indicated that teachers’ workloads stress had a significant negative relationship with job satisfaction score and Yusuf, Olufunke and Valentine (2015) whose findings revealed that lack of Job satisfaction and inadequate skill facilities were major causes of stress among primary school teachers. This means that it is important to reduce workload with higher control in monitoring attendance of teachers to classes. Naturally, when job demand is high, it weakens teachers’, exhausts them and their input will be low, but in some individuals/teachers, who are naturally lazy and exhibits signs of redundancy in working, high job demands quickens them, encourages them to put in more effort. These categories of lazy ones, if they do not hear that supervisors are coming to school, they will not write their lesson plans, update their records or even go to teach their lessons. Their class attendance used to be poor, most especially, from teacher’s that are supposed to be punctual to conduct role calls in their classrooms. High job demand motivates teachers to put in their best especially if there is a threat to withhold salary or incentives if they failed to meet up with deadline.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the research findings indicate that job demand plays a crucial role in predicting teachers' productivity. The study delved into various aspects of teacher productivity, including tasks like lesson note preparation, the efficient utilization of scheme of work, students' work, and more, emphasizing their significance in the educational system. This study is distinctive in that it is the first to examine the relationship between job demands and teachers' productivity specifically in the context of senior secondary schools in North-East, Nigeria.

Recommendation

On the basis of the finding of this study, the following recommendations were made.

- i. Educational institutions and policymakers are advised to consider the substantial impact of job demands on teachers' productivity and to take measures to alleviate excessive workloads.
- ii. Teachers are encouraged to prioritize the effective preparation of lesson notes and the efficient use of scheme of work to enhance their productivity, thus contributing to improved educational outcomes.
- iii. Schools are urged to provide support and allocate resources to help teachers manage the demands of their profession, ensuring they can maintain a high level of productivity.

References

- Ary, D., Jacobs, L.C., Razavieh, A. & Sorensen, C. K. (2009). *Introduction to Research in Education (8th ed)*. Wadsworth, CA, USA. P.379. [https:// www. Amazon.com/introduction-research- education -Donald-Ary/dp/0495601225](https://www.amazon.com/introduction-research-education-Donald-Ary/dp/0495601225).
- Ayeni, A.A. (2020). Teachers' capacity building and productivity in secondary schools in Ondo North Senatorial District of Ondo State, Nigeria. *Innovative Studies: International Journal (ISIJ)*, 3(1), 2–7.
- Bakker, A. B & Demerouti, E. (2018). *Multiple levels in job demands –resources theory: Implications for employee well-being and performance*. Handbook of well –being, SaltLake city, UT: DEF publishers: Doi: nobascholar.com.
- Borg, W.R., & Gall, M.D. (1983). *Educational research; An Introduction*. United States of America. (4th ed). [https://books.google.com.books.about.education](https://books.google.com/books/about/education).
- Chen, Y., Li, S., Xia, Q., & He, C. (2017). The relationship between job demands and employees' counter productive work behaviors: The mediating job demands and employees' counter productive work behaviours, The Mediating Effects of psychological detachment and job anxiety. *Journal List from Leaders in Psychology*, <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/pmc56703181>.
- Elujekwute, E.C., Nyitar, R.H. & Elujekwute, L.A., (2021). Occupational stress and teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Makurdi Educational Zone of Benue State, Nigeria. *Sapientia Global Journal of Arts, Humanities Development Studies*, 4(1), 78 – 79.
- Kabir, F.S. (2019). Relationship between jobs demand, workload and job satisfaction among teachers in public secondary schools in Kaduna metropolis, Nigeria. *Journal of Science Education and Technology*, 7(4),42-49. www.atbuftejoste.com
- Kanja, J.M., Tabitha, D.W. & Cecilia, D.M. (2022). Teachers' workload stress as a correlate of job satisfaction in international secondary schools in Nairobi City County, Kenya. *Journal of Advanced Research in Social Science and Humanities*, 8(4), 1-6. DOI; <https://doi.org/10.53555/musah.v8:4.1251>.
- Ndambo, S.M., Maithya, P. & Mwaura, K. (2021). Effects of teaching workload on teachers' performancne in public secondary schools in Kitui County. *International Journal of Innovative Research and Development*, 10(8): 24-34.

- Tijani, A.A. & Abdullahi, N.J.K. (2021). Economic recession as correlate of teacher Productivity in Kwara State Secondary Schools, Nigeria. *Kashere Journal of Education (KJE)*, 2(1), 129-137. [https:// www. researchgate.net](https://www.researchgate.net).
- Usoro, A.A. (2018). Occupational stress and the job effectiveness of federal university lecturers in Cross River and Akwa Ibom States, Nigeria. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 10(14), 79-84. www.iiste.org. ISSN 2222-1905 (paper) ISSN 2222-2849 (online).
- Uwannah, N.C., Eteete, M.A & Mark, O.G. (2019). Work environment, compensation and teachers' productivity; Evidence from Ogun State, Nigeria. *European Journal of Scientific Research*, 154 (1), 83-93. <http://www.europeanjournalofscientificresearch>.
- Vissy, A. & Arum, E.H. (2018). The relation of job demands to teacher and staff stress: Impact of a job crafting intervention in advanced in social science. *Education and Humanities Research*, 229. Doi:2991/icap-18.2019.80,
- Yusuf, F. A., Olufunke, Y. R. & Valentine, M. D. (2015). Causes and impact of stress on teachers' productivity as expressed by primary school teachers in Nigeria. *Creative Education*, 6 (18), 1937-1942. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4236/ce.2015.618199>